

GC-MS-Based Phytochemical Profiling and in Vitro Assessment of the Antibacterial and Anti-Inflammatory Activities of *Onosma Hispida*

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ABSTRACT

Medicinal plants play a vital role in healing of various diseases. *Onosma hispida* belongs to genus *Onosma*, family *Boraginaceae*. This research was aimed to determine the phytochemical compounds and their biological activities of the plant. Gas Chromatography Mass Spectrometry (GC-MS) was used for phytochemical analysis. The methanolic extract was used against antibacterial and anti-inflammatory activities during standard in-vitro tests. The results indicated moderated anti-inflammatory activity in chemiluminescence protocol while plant extract showed a significant activity against *Staphylococcus aureus* among five bacterial strains through disc diffusion method. The analysis of the GC-MS displayed 29 phytochemical compounds in *n*-hexane fraction of medicinal plant e.g. β -pinene, *n*-hexadecanoic acid, octacosane, eicosane, phytol. These results further confirm the presence of potential source of bioactive compounds used in pharmaceutical and ethno-botanical therapeutic applications.

1. Introduction

Plants, animals and microorganisms are primary source of natural products. Plants have been widely used as traditional herbal remedies to cure a variety of medical conditions, and their various natural components have influenced the creation of novel medications (Chaachouay *et al.*, 2024). Sometimes plants produce secondary metabolites (SMs) which are by products of primary metabolic process. SMs are referred to be "secondary compounds" since they do not directly affect the plant growth, development and metabolism but are crucial to plant defense mechanisms. The main purpose of SMs is to enhance plant development and survival in challenging environments. These days, secondary metabolites (SMs) are employed as significant natural medications such as antibiotics, immune suppressants, anticancer and antidiabetic drugs. They are also helpful in evaluating the quality of medicinal substances (Khare *et al.*, 2020; Pant *et al.*, 2020) *Onosma* species are the member of *Boraginaceae* family. This family comprises 90-120 genera and more than two hundred species, categorized into 5 subfamilies i.e *Cordioideae*, *Ehretioideae*, *Lennoideae*, *Hydrophylloideae* and *Boraginoideae* (Jabbar *et al.*, 2022).

Onosma is the major genera in tribe Lithospermeae Dumort. The Boraginaceae family has more than 230 species in Europe and Asia. There are several species of *Onosma* found all over the world, including 105 species in Turkey, 54 species in Iran, 8 species in Pakistan, more than 15 species in India, and 33 and 34 species in Russia and neighboring republics. There are now approximately 250 species in this genus as a result of numerous studies that have been directed in recent years Linnaeus proposed the botanical term "*Onosma*" for this genus, derived from Greek word "Osma" or "Osme" which means smell or scent. All species are located in dry or damp areas, usually in stone cracks due to which they are known as rockery plants (Kumar *et al.*, 2022).

The *Onosma* genus has been found to comprise over 200 compounds including flavonoid 30, naphthoquinone 33, fatty acids 9, alkaloids 20, hydrocarbon 23, carboxylic acid 11, terpenoids 10, phenolic, ester 17, aromatics 12 and most noteworthy of them are ferulic acid, rosmarinic acid, caffeic acid, protocatechuic acid (Jabbar *et al.*, 2022).

Onosma hispida is the species of genus *onosma* and belongs to family boraginaceae. It is referred to generally as Bristly *onosma*. In Urdu *Onosma hispida* is called Soi and other local names are Kangmar, Ladakh, Demok in balti Ratanjot, Ratmundi, Hundheu in kashmiri language Sharong, Gao saban in Pashto and yarrilang in brahvi (Hussain *et al.*, 2021; Ullah *et al.*, 2024).

Onosma hispida is an annual plant with a prominent taproot that can grow as tall as 70 cm in height. It is widely distributed in the Afghanistan, Africa, Russia, Syria, Turkey, South West Asia Mongolia, Iran, South Europe, India and northern areas of Pakistan usually present at Balochistan, Chitral, Karrum, Landikotal, Kashmir, Skardu, Swat and Kaghan. It is used in the treatment of eye diseases, bronchitis, stangury, fever, derangements of the blood, thirst, itch, abdominal pain, urinary calculi, wounds, piles, leucoderma and possesses alexipharmic, cooling, laxative, and anthalminitic properties. Its blossoms are used to treat

heart conditions and rheumatism as a heart tonic and stimulant. The plant produces therapeutic oil, lipids, and a good color for wool and hair (Ahmad *et al.*, 2023; Ahmad *et al.*, 2005; Ahmad *et al.*, 2010).

GC-MS is a significant procedure that has been modified to assess various phytoconstituents in different plant extracts together with their structures. It integrates a combination of two analytical methods into one method analyzing mixtures of chemical compounds. Components of the mixture are separated using gas chromatography and each of the components is analyzed using mass spectroscopy. The chemical investigations have revealed that it primarily contains volatile substances, cardenolides, pregnane and glycosides, majority of volatile constituents are long chain of unsaturated fatty acids that play important role within the biological systems due to the fact that they are building blocks of most of the valuable compounds and are also a considerable source of energy (Gomathi *et al.*, 2015; Thamer *et al.*, 2023).

Onosma hispida has traditionally been employed in herbal medication for the treatment of various diseases including inflammation, wound healing, infections and gastrointestinal disorders. Although several studies have reported the presence of phytochemicals and certain pharmacological properties of the plant, the available scientific literature remains limited. The previous investigations have focused on crude extract and limited evaluation of phytochemical screening and biological potential.

The current study is mainly focused on identification of volatile constituents and antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory activities. In particular, there is a lack of comprehensive studies on volatile chemical profile of *onosma hispida* collected from the ecological specific region of Balochistan, where it depends on climatic and geographical conditions.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Sample Collection and Preparation

The Plant samples of *Onosma hispida* were obtained from Ziarat, Balochistan, Pakistan and verified by Dr. Ayesha Masood, Assistant Professor, Botany department, University of Balochistan, Quetta. The fresh samples of plant were collected and dried in shade. After drying, these samples were grinded into powder with a pestle and mortar. The sample was placed in a container and 90% methanol was added. Container was sealed and leaved in a cool dark place and shaking it occasionally, for filtration process the Whatman filter paper was used to separate liquid extract from the plant residue. The obtained filtrates were

evaporated by via rotary evaporator. The sample was three times extracted using methanol to get maximum chemical constituents during the extraction process. The resulting extract was fractionated into n-hexane and ethyl acetate.

2.2. Gas Chromatography Mass Spectrometry (GC-MS) Analysis

The identification of chemical constituents of various fractions was analyzed through GC-MS. The retention times were determined by gas chromatography (GC), whereas molecular and fragment ion peaks were measured by Mass spectrometry (MS). Agilent (7890B) GC gas chromatograph integrated with (MSD) mass selective detector (5977B). Separation was performed using DB-5MS capillary column (30 m Length \times 0.25mm internal diameter \times 0.25 μ m film thickness). For stationary Phase the column was filled with 5% Phenylmethyl siloxan, whereas helium gas served as mobile phase which transport the sample efficiently through the column. The 2 μ l of sample was used in this process. In the case of Mass spectrometry, the temperature of the oven was first kept at 50 °C for 3 minutes and then increased to 300°C, maximum recorded oven pressure and temperature were 9.05 psi at 340 °C with a total running time of 30 minutes. The electron impact ionization at -70 eV was employed for mass detection. The spectra were detected and aligned with NIST Library 20.0 (Kanthal *et al.*, 2014; Enerijiofi *et al.*, 2021; Maharjan *et al.*, 2025; Yadav *et al.*, 2026).

2.3 Antibacterial assay

Antibacterial activity of the sample was tested through disc diffusion technique against five species of bacteria. The two *Bacillus subtilis*, *Stphylococcus aureus* gram-positive bacteria and three *Escherichia coli*, *Pseudomonas aeriginosa*, *Salmonella typhi* gram-negative bacteria were selected to analyze antibacterial activity. The cultures were distributed evenly on the media surface and the discs of sterile filter papers were wetted in the sample. The saturated filter paper discs were then placed on the culture media and sterile forceps used to press on the saturated discs to make full contact with the media surface. The antibiotic disc (Ofloxacin) was used as a standard. The Plates were inoculated for a period of 24 hours according to the optimal growth conditions at temperature of 37°C. After 24 hours plates were examined for the presence of circular zone of inhibition measured in millimeter with the help of caliper (Shende *et al.*, 2023; Bizuayehu *et al.*, 2025).

2.4 Anti-inflammatory Activity

The anti- inflammatory potential of extract was measured via an Oxidative burst assay by performing Chemiluminscence method. Diluted whole blood (25 μ L) in HBSS++ was pre-

incubated with 25 μ L of plant extract in 96-well half area plate at 37 °C for 15 minutes in luminometers thermostat chamber. The Oxidative burst was triggered by adding 25 μ L of Serum Opsonized Zymosan (SOZ). For the detection of reaction Luminol (25 μ L) was added to probe for intracellular reactive oxygen species (ROS) except blank wells contained only HBSS++. ROS levels were measure in Relative Light Unit (RLU) using Luminometer. Ibuprofen IC₅₀11.2 \pm 1.9 was as standard drug (Achakzai *et al.*, 2020).

2.5 FTIR Analysis

The FTIR is the most applicable method for determining the functional group present in the compound. Methanolic extract and ethyl acetate, n-hexane fractions of *Onosma hispidum* were analyzed for the functional groups. The peak values were recorded between 4000-400 cm⁻¹ spectral ranges (Kanwal *et al.*, 2025).

3. Result and Discussion

3.1 GC-MS Analysis

The *Onosma hispidum* n-hexane fraction was examined through GC-MS method. The compounds list along with their molecular formula, molecular weight and retention time, area of sum % peaks are given in (Table 1). The chromatogram of GC displayed the relative concentration of each compound verses retention time. The chromatogram included as (Figure 1). The data obtained from the present work showed the presence of 29 compounds including β -Pinene, n-hexadecanoic acid, Stearic acid, Hexacosane and Phytol etc. Among them β -Pinene possesses antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory and antioxidant, hexadecanoic acid has antibacterial potential and phytol has good potential antioxidant, anti-inflammatory. The existence of these biologically active phytochemicals in n-hexane fraction of the plan *O.hispida* confirms its possible medicinal significance (Salehi *et al.*, 2019; Purushothaman *et al.*, 2024; Islam *et al.*, 2018).

Table 1. List of Identified Compounds by GC-MS analysis

No #	Retention Time	Name of Compounds	Area sum%	Molecular formula	Molecular weight
1	3.758	β -Pinene	32.98	C ₁₀ H ₁₆	136.23
2	5.902	n-Hexadecanoic acid	5.02	C ₁₆ H ₃₂ O ₂	256.42
3	6.854	Stearic Acid	0.03	C ₁₈ H ₃₆ O ₂	284.48
4	8.347	Pentadecane, 8-hexyl-	0.05	C ₂₁ H ₄₄	296.6
5	10.147	Hexacosane	0.09	C ₂₆ H ₅₄	366.7

6	11.199	Octadecane, 2-methyl-	0.02	C ₁₉ H ₄₀	268.52
7	11.700	Docosane, 11-butyl-	0.03	C ₂₆ H ₅₄	366.7
8	11.797	Heptadecane, 9-octyl-	0.03	C ₂₅ H ₅₂	352.68
9	12.365	Decane, 3,8-dimethyl-	0.04	C ₁₂ H ₂₆	170.34
10	12.860	Nonane, 5-butyl-	0.21	C ₁₃ H ₂₈	184.36
11	13.507	20.Xi.-Lanosta-7,9(11)-diene-3.beta.,18,20-triol	0.23	C ₃₀ H ₅₀ O ₃	458.72
12	15.404	13,17,21-Trimethylheptatriacont	0.03	C ₄₀ H ₈₂	563.0791
13	17.174	Hexadecane, 2,6,10,14-tetramethyl-	0.20	C ₂₀ H ₄₂	282.55
14	17.362	Triacontane	1.60	C ₃₀ H ₆₂	422.8
15	18.582	Heneicosane	1.16	C ₂₁ H ₄₄	296.58
16	18.788	Hentriacontane	1.74	C ₃₁ H ₆₄	436.85
17	18.999	17,21Dimethylheptatriacontane	0.75	C ₃₉ H ₈₀	549.05
18	19.138	11-Methyltricosane	0.46	C ₂₄ H ₅₀	338.65
19	19.271	Nonadecane, 3-methyl-	0.75	C ₂₀ H ₄₂	282.55
20	19.507	Nonadecane, 9-methyl-	0.84	C ₂₀ H ₄₂	282.55
21	19.573	Octadecane, 3-methyl-	0.68	C ₁₉ H ₂₄	268.52
22	19.633	11-Methylpentacosane	0.35	C ₁₆ H ₃₄	226.44
23	19.815	Heneicosane, 11-decyl-	0.35	C ₃₁ H ₆₄	436.84
24	20.775	Hexadecane, 2,6,10,14-tetramethyl-	0.12	C ₂₀ H ₄₂	282.55
25	20.938	Octadecane, 2-methyl-	1.53	C ₁₉ H ₂₄	268.52
26	22.008	Pentacosane	0.02	C ₂₅ H ₅₂	352.68
27	23.531	Octacosane	2.62	C ₂₈ H ₅₈	394.77
28	24.298	Eicosane	0.02	C ₂₀ H ₄₂	282.55
29	28.038	Phytol	3.12	C ₂₀ H ₄₀ O	296.54

Figure1. Gas Chromatography Mass Spectrometry (GC-MS) chromatogram of *O.hispida* n-hexane fraction

3.2 Antibacterial Activity

The methanolic extract of *Onosma hispida* was examined for antibacterial activity against 5 bacterial species with disc diffusion method. The *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Escherichia coli*, *Bacillus subtilis*, *Salmonella typh* and *pseudomonas aerginosai* were selected to analyze antibacterial activity. It showed significant activity against *S. aureus* (24 mm inhibition zone) whereas it has not shown activity for the remaining four species. The results are incorporated in (Table 2).

The results resemble with the findings of Bangulzai *et al.*, 2017 during the study of anti-bacterial activity of *Ephidra intermedia*. Which revealed a significant activity against *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Escherichia coli*, *Psudomonas fluorescence* and *Bacillus subtilis* in various extracts. Mokhtar *et al.*, 2023 they concluded that the methanolic extract of *Cymbopogon schoenanthus* (L.) exhibit antibacterial activity against all Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacterial strains. *Bacillus cereus* had the greatest inhibitory effect followed by *Stphylococcus aureus*, *Klebsiella pneumonia* and *Escherichia coli* (Mokhtar *et al.*, 2023). The antibacterial activity of these and the other plants are probably due to the avability of alkaloids, phenolic acids, terpenoids, flavonoids and other biologically active substances that possess good antimicrobial potential (Álvarez-Martínez *et al.*, 2021; Asghar *et al.*, 2022; Barbieri *et al.*, 2017; Plabon *et al.*, 2021). The bioactive substances inhibit bacteria in various ways such as preventing protein formation, disrupting the cell membrane, preventing cell wall formation and interference with many other metabolic processes (Górniak *et al.*, 2019; Chandra *et al.*, 2020; Sharma *et al.*, 2017; AlSheikh *et al.*, 2020).

Table 2. Antibacterial activity of *Onosma hispida* extract 3000µg/ml, Ofloxacin 50µg/ml concentration

Bacterial species	Inhibition zone of Methanolic extract (mm)	Inhibition zone of Drug (Ofloxacin)(mm)
<i>Escherichia coli</i> ATCC 25922	0	89.33
<i>Bacillus subtilis</i> ATCC 23857	0	84.29
<i>Stphylococcus aureus</i> NCTC 13297	24mm	26mm
<i>Pseudomonas aerginosa</i> ATCC 10145	0	91.63
<i>Salmonella typhi</i> ATCC 14028	0	91.89

3.3 Anti-inflammatory Assay

Anti-inflammatory assay of *O.hispida* was determined through oxidative burst by Chemiluminescence technique. The results showed moderate activity against (ROS) reactive oxygen reactive oxygen species production given in (Table 3) as compared to Ibuprofen. Anti-inflammatory and pain-relieving compounds are used to promote immune system, to treat pain, snakebites, asthma and skin conditions. The alkaloids were used to give the fundamental backbone to the creation of a wide range of antibiotics with varied activities. Plant extract evaluated to determine its in vitro anti-inflammatory properties by conventional methods including denaturation of proteins, proteinase inhibition, and heat-induced hemolysis. The protein denaturation is a significant cause of inflammation in diabetes, rheumatoid, arthritis and cancer. The inflammatory disorders might be minimized by preventing protein denaturation. Chemical compounds which inhibit protein denaturation could be useful in the anti-inflammatory drugs. Proteinase is important in the arthritic condition. Neutrophils contain large amounts of a serine proteinase in its lysosomal granules. It has been reported in the previous literature that the leukocyte proteinase is relevant in the pathogenesis of tissue damage in the case of inflammatory reactions; therefore, the use of proteinase inhibitors is associated with a high level of protection. The limited studies have been conducted on the anti-inflammatory effect of *Achilea* species. Nevertheless, the literature indicates genus achillea is popular because it possesses anti-inflammatory potential attributed to its composition tophenolics, flavonoids, tannins, saponins, terpenoids, lignans, essential oil, and occasionally triterpenes (Serino *et al.*, 2021; Othman *et al.*, 2019).

Table 3. Anti-inflammatory activity of *O. hispida* extract

Extract/ Std. drug	Conc. ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	% inhibition/stimulation	IC ₅₀ \pm SD ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)
<i>O. hispida</i> extract	250 $\mu\text{g/ml}$	80.82%	53.88 \pm 1.06 $\mu\text{g/ml}$
Ibuprofen	-	-	11.2 \pm 1.9 $\mu\text{g/ml}$

3.4 FTIR Analysis

The methanolic extract and n-hexane, ethyl acetate fractions of *O. hispida* has been done with the Fourier Transform Infrared spectroscopy at 400 to 4000 cm^{-1} form which following results have been obtained included in (figure1, 2 & 3).

Figure 1: FTIR peaks for Methanolic extract

Figure 2: FTIR peaks for n-hexane

Figure 3: FTIR peaks for Ethyl acetate

4. Conclusion

This study of plant revealed that plant *Onosma hispida* collected from Ziarat Valley, are rich in phytochemical constituents and show a significant biological property. The methanolic extract of the plants exhibited moderate anti-inflammatory effects as compared to Ibuprofen during chemiluminescence assay and demonstrated antibacterial effects against single bacteria (*Staphylococcus aureus*) as compared to Ofloxacin among five strains by using disc diffusion approach. GC-MS profiling of n-hexane fraction revealed 29 phytochemical compounds, including β -pinene, n-hexadecanoic acid, octacosane, eicosane, and phytol, which are likely responsible for biological activities. The results validate the indigenous medicinal application of *Onosma hispida* plant and suggest promise as a source of its natural therapeutic agents. This research may open a new vista for the researchers and pharmaceutical industries to elucidate the mechanisms of action of these compounds and assess their clinical applicability. Furthermore, studies are recommended to isolate and characterized biologically active compounds and to assess their therapeutic potential.

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